

Mechanistic study of oxidative transformation of hetero aromatic stimulant, 1,3,7-trimethyl uric acid by potassium permanganate in perchloric acid medium – A kinetic study

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of 1,3,7-trimethyl uric acid (Caffeine) by potassium permanganate in acidic medium was studied spectrophotometrically. The reaction followed first order kinetics with respect to [permanganate ion] and the activation parameters of the reaction were calculated and discussed. The reaction constants involved in the mechanisms were calculated. The permanganate ion has a better oxidising capacity in acid medium than in alkaline medium. The oxidation products were confirmed through IR, NMR and Mass spectral investigations and two of them have been investigated in the light of non-linear optical (NLO) applications and found suitable for second harmonic generation (SHG) applications.

Keywords : Kinetics, oxidation, Caffeine, acidic $MnO_4(HMnO_4)$.

Introduction

During the oxidation by permanganate, it is evident that the manganese(VII) is reduced to various oxidation states in acidic, alkaline and neutral media. Out of the six oxidation states of manganese¹ from +2 to +7, permanganate Mn^{VII} , is the most powerful oxidant in dilute acid medium with reduction potentials 1.69 V of Mn^{VII}/Mn^{IV} couple and 1.51 V of Mn^{VII}/Mn^{II} couple. The manganese chemistry involved in these multistep redox reactions provides an important source of information as the manganese intermediates are relatively easy to identify when they have sufficiently long life times. Oxidation states of the intermediates permit useful conclusions to be drawn for the possible mechanism, including the nature of intermediates.

Oxidation or the permanganate ion is applied extensively in organic syntheses²⁻⁸ especially since the advent of phase transfer catalysis^{4,5,7}. Kinetic studies are important sources of mechanistic information on the reactions, as demonstrated by the results referring to unsaturated acids both in aqueous^{2,4,8}, a non-aqueous media⁹.

Furthermore, the mechanism by which this multivalent oxidant oxidizes a substrate depends not only on the substrate but also on the medium¹⁰ used for the study

Permanganate ion in an acidic medium has been used extensively as a potent oxidant for studying the oxidation kinetics of many organic substrates. In some cases the mechanistic approach is based on the intermediate complex formation and in others, the results are interpreted by a free radical mechanism. The mechanism suggested by various authors are not uniform, indicating that a wide variety of mechanisms are possible depending on the nature of the reactive species of permanganate as well as the substrate.

Caffeine is a naturally occurring purine base present in coffee, tea, cocoa and nuts. Caffeine (1,3,7-trimethyluric acid) a cyclic aromatic compound containing nitrogen. Caffeine has a drastic stimulating effect on people, and both tea and coffee have been consumed for centuries for this effect. In this century, caffeine has been marketed by itself and in combination with other ingredients for use as a stimulant by those who do not like coffee or cannot conveniently drink a beverage until recently the caffeine sold in this way was prepared from coca fruits. Foods and beverages that contain purine alkaloids such as coffee, tea, soft drinks, cocoa and chocolate enjoy immense popularity worldwide. The presence of methyl xanthenes such as caffeine theobromine and theophylline makes an im-

portant contribution to the organoleptic quality of these products. For instance in case of coffee, caffeine can account for 10–30% of the bitter taste (Viani, 1988). Because of its wide use in foods, beverages and medicinal preparations, caffeine represents one of the most intensely investigated chemicals for toxicological and physiological effects with positive behavioral characteristics that include alertness, wellbeing, motivation and increased concentration (Barone and Grice, 1994)¹¹. Because of the vast consumption of caffeine-containing beverages, research has focused attention on its physiological effects. It has been reported that a number of biochemical reactions in our body generate reactive oxygen species mainly comprising free radicals and excited states, capable of damaging crucial biomolecules. The major reactive oxygen species of interest in oxidative stress and radiation damage are viz. hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$), superoxide (O_2^-), hydrated electron (e_{aq}^-), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), peroxy radical (ROO') etc. are capable of damaging crucial biomolecules such as DNA, proteins and membrane lipids^{12,13}. These radicals are not effectively scavenged by the antioxidant defense system in the tissues, oxidative stress results^{14,15}. Caffeine has been reported^{15,19} to have significant abilities to scavenge highly reactive free radicals and excited states of oxygen and to protect crucial biological molecules against these species. Antioxidant

No studies have been reported on the oxidation of caffeine by other oxidants. In view of the lack of reports in the literature on the oxidation of caffeine by acidic KMnO_4 , we have selected caffeine as a substrate for the oxidation. The present study deals with the kinetics of the oxidation of caffeine by KMnO_4 in acid medium to arrive at a plausible mechanism and to determine the active species of permanganate in such media.

Results

Different sets of reaction mixtures containing excess $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ over $[\text{caffeine}]$ were mixed in the presence of 2 mol dm^{-3} perchloric acid and adjusted to an ionic strength of 2.5 mol dm^{-3} and were kept for 12 h in an inert atmosphere at 25 °C. After completion of the reaction, the remaining permanganate was then determined spectrophotometrically.

The results indicated that, one mole of caffeine was consumed by one mole of permanganate as in eq. (1). The main oxidation products were identified as 1,3-dimethyl alloxan, N-methyl urea (monomethyl urea) and manganese(II). Methyl urea or N-methyl urea was identified by a spot test²² and m.p. 98 °C. It is a colorless powder with needle shaped crystals. The other product, manganese(II) in acid medium was analysed using EDTA solution with Erichrome black-T as indicator^{20(b)}.

ability of caffeine is similar to that of the established biological antioxidant glutathione and significantly much higher than that of ascorbic acid¹⁹.

The product 1,3-dimethyl alloxan is highly unstable and decomposes immediately in aqueous media to give N,N'-dimethyl urea and mesoxalic acid as eq. (2).

Dimethyl urea is in the form of white flakes, soluble in water with melting point 104 °C. Both N,N'-dimethyl urea and N-methyl urea are derivatives of urea with amine like odour. Mesoxalic acid (molecular formula, C₃H₂O₅) is both a dicarboxylic acid and ketonic acid which readily absorbs and reacts with water to form a product called monohydrate of mesoxalic acid, HO-(C=O)-(OH)₂-(C=O)-OH²³ [eq. (3)].

N-Methyl urea (1-methyl urea) and N,N'-dimethyl (1,3-dimethyl urea) urea were further confirmed through FTIR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectrums²⁴.

N,N'-Dimethyl urea :

FTIR : (KBr), C=O stretching vibration at 1679 cm⁻¹, N-H stretching vibration at 3375 cm⁻¹ with a single broad band and C-H stretching vibration at 2960 cm⁻¹ for CH₃; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ_H : 5.69 (two -NH protons), 2.54 (two -CH₃ protons) *m/z*; Found : M⁺• 88 (49.5%). C₃H₈N₂O requires : 88 (Fragmentation : ⁺•CONHCH₃ *m/z* 58 (50%), ⁺•CNHCH₃ *m/z* 42 (2%), ⁺•NHCH₃ *m/z* 30 (100%); ⁺•CH₃ *m/z* 15 (20%).

N-Methyl urea :

FTIR : (KBr), C=O stretching vibration at 1670 cm⁻¹, NH₂ stretching vibrations at 3229 and 3430 cm⁻¹ and C-H stretching vibration band at 2960 cm⁻¹ antisymmetric and 2874 cm⁻¹ symmetric vibrations for -CH₃; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ_H : 5 to 6.0 (two -NH₂ protons), 3.5 (one -NH proton), 2.5 (one -CH₃ proton) *m/z*; Found : M⁺• 74 (40%). C₂H₆N₂O requires : 74 (Fragmentation : ⁺•CONHCH₃ *m/z* 58 (5%), ⁺•CNHCH₃ *m/z* 42 (60%), ⁺•NHCH₃ *m/z* 30 (100%), ⁺•CH₃ *m/z* 15 (15%).

Applications of urea derivatives :

1,1-Dimethyl urea (H₂NCON(CH₃)₂) and 1,3-dimethyl urea (CH₃HNCONHCH₃) have been investigated in the light of NLO applications and few of them found suitable for second harmonic generation (SHG) applications²⁵. N-Methyl urea (H₃CNHCONH₂) is one of the promising organic nonlinear optical materials for ultraviolet conversion²⁶. Non-linear optical (NLO) properties of 1,3-dimethyl urea have been studied in detail²⁷.

Reaction orders :

The order each in caffeine and perchloric acid was investigated by varying one of these concentrations while keeping all other concentrations and conditions constant and studying the effect of its concentration on the rate of the reaction. The resulting data were employed to plot log *k*_{obs} versus log concentration graphs and the orders were obtained from such graphs.

Effect of [MnO₄⁻] :

Kinetic data were collected for initial [MnO₄⁻] in the (0.40–4.0) × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ range. In acid medium, MnO₄⁻ follow first order kinetics (Fig. 1).

Effect of [Caffeine] :

The concentration of caffeine was varied in the range of (0.2–2.0) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ keeping all other reactants concentrations and conditions constant. In an acid medium the *k* values increased with increase in concentration of caffeine indicating first order (1.20, Table 1) dependence on [Caf.] (*r* > 0.9990, *s* ≤ 0.4325).

Effect of [acid] :

To study the effect of [H⁺], on the rate of the reaction, the [H⁺] was varied from (0.3–3.0) mol dm⁻³ at a constant concentration of MnO₄⁻ and caffeine, maintaining a constant ionic strength of 2.5 mol dm⁻³. It was found that the rate increased with increase of H⁺ concentration. The order was less than unity (0.4982, Table 1) (*r* > 0.99068, *s* ≤ 1.6761).

Effect of ionic strength (I) and dielectric constant (D) of the medium :

To study the effect of ionic strength, the concentration of sodium perchlorate was varied from (0.25–2.5) mol dm⁻³ at constant concentrations of oxidant, caffeine and perchloric acid. The ionic strength had negligible effect on the rate of the reaction. The relative permittivity effect (*D*) was studied by varying acetic acid-water content, keeping all other conditions constant. No significant effect was observed on the rate of the reaction.

Effect of addition of product :

The addition of the products such as N-methyl urea (1-methyl urea) and N,N'-dimethyl (1,3-dimethyl urea) urea, meso oxalic acid and Mn^{II} did not show any significant on the rate of the reaction.

Fig. 1. First order plot of $\log (A_t - A_{00})$ versus time in acid medium. $[\text{Caf.}] = 1.2 \times 10^{-2}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 2.0$ and $I = 2.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{MnO}_4^-] \times 10^4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (1) 0.4; (2) 1.0; (3) 2.0; (4) 3.0; (5) 4.0.

Table 1. Effect of [Caffeine], $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ on the oxidation of caffeine by acidified permanganate at 25 °C (Temp. 25 °C; $I = 2.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)

$[\text{Caf.}] \times 10^2$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[\text{MnO}_4^-] \times 10^4$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[\text{H}^+]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$k \times 10^3$ (s^{-1}) Expt. ^a
2.0	2.0	2.0	0.21
0.6	2.0	2.0	0.89
1.2	2.0	2.0	1.95
1.6	2.0	2.0	2.68
2.0	2.0	2.0	3.42
1.2	0.4	2.0	2.02
1.2	1.0	2.0	1.97
1.2	2.0	2.0	1.98
1.2	3.0	2.0	2.01
1.2	4.0	2.0	2.02
1.2	2.0	0.3	0.88
1.2	2.0	1.0	1.50
1.2	2.0	2.0	2.02
1.2	2.0	2.5	2.67
1.2	2.0	3.0	2.74

^aExperimental and calculated error $\pm 5\%$.

Polymerization study :

To test for free radical intervention, the reaction mixture containing acrylonitrile was kept for 24 h. On dilution with methanol, no precipitate resulted indicating no polymerization of acrylonitrile. This observation indicates that the oxidation of caffeine by acidic potassium permanganate proceeds through the absence of polymer formation and, as well, any intervention of free radicals. There is evidence of polymerization with acrylonitrile in the earlier studies²⁸.

Effect of temperature (T) :

The effect of temperature on the reaction was studied at four different temperatures. The rate increased with an increase in temperature. The Arrhenius plot was drawn for the variation of k_{obs} with temperature. The energy of activation was evaluated from the plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/T$ ($r \leq 0.9968$, $s \leq 2.9815$) and other activation parameters were calculated which are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Thermodynamic activation parameters for the oxidation of caffeine by acidic KMnO_4

Activation parameters	
E_a (kJ mol^{-1})	105 ± 5
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	103 ± 5
ΔS^\ddagger ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$)	-48 ± 2
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	89 ± 4

^aError $\pm 5\%$.

Fig. 2. Spectroscopic changes occurring in the oxidation Caffeine by permanganate with $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$, $[\text{Caf.}] = 1.2 \times 10^{-2}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 2.0$ and $I = 2.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 25°C (scanning time interval : 1 min).

Discussion

The permanganate ion, MnO_4^- , is a powerful oxidising agent in acidic medium. Oxidation of caffeine by permanganate in HClO_4 medium is a non-complementary reaction in which the oxidant undergoes one equivalent change. In this experiment reaction between caffeine and MnO_4^- had a stoichiometry of 1 : 1 with first order dependence on $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ and [caffeine] and fractional order dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$. Stoichiometric studies revealed 1-equivalent changes in Mn^{VII} . Hence the formation of Mn^{IV} as a reduced product of Mn^{VII} in the reaction was excluded, although forma-

tion of Mn^{IV} has been observed in earlier studies²⁶. The strong reducing character of caffeine was evident in the reduction of Mn^{VII} to Mn^{II} in HClO_4 medium.

The active species of permanganate in aqueous acid medium may be deduced from the dependence of the rate on $[\text{H}^+]$ in the reaction medium. The apparent order of less than unity in $[\text{H}^+]$ may be an indication of permanganate species as permanganic acid. In acid medium, permanganic acid HMnO_4 is a more efficient oxidant species of manganese(VII) than permanganate ion^{29,30}. In addition it has been observed that the reaction rate increased with increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ and was tending to attain a limiting value at high acidities. The plot of k_{obs} versus $[\text{H}^+]$ in acid medium is a curve of decreasing slope (convex to the rate axis) and passing through the origin (Fig. 3) from which it can be inferred³¹ that a rapid equilibrium between the protonated and unprotonated form is involved. At higher acidities protonation is almost complete, leading to the limiting rate, which indicates that only the protonated form is active. The ionic strength effect on the rate of the reaction also confirms HMnO_4 as the active species of MnO_4^- . Thus the acid permanganate equilibrium is represented as

where K is the formation constant of HMnO_4 .

Fig. 3. The plot of k_{obs} versus $[\text{H}^+]$, a curve of decreasing slope (convex to the rate axis) (conditions as in Table 1).

MECHANISM

Scheme 1

Based on the experimental results, the following mechanism can be proposed in which all the observed orders with respect to each constituent such as [oxidant], [reductant] and $[H^+]$ may be well accommodated. The results suggest the formation of protonated form of permanganate as the active species of MnO_4^- in a prior equilibrium, which reacts with one mole of caffeine in a rate determining step to give a oxidized intermediate product of caffeine and reduced intermediate, Mn^V . The intermediate, Mn^V being very active and unstable in acid medium, reacts further

with oxidized intermediate product of caffeine to give one more intermediate product and it itself is further reduced in a fast step to Mn^{III} . Mn^{III} oxidized the intermediate product to 1,3-dimethyl alloxan and monomethyl urea and itself subsequently reduced to the end product, Mn^{II} in further fast step satisfying stoichiometric observations. The mechanism is proposed in Scheme 1.

Further as dimethyl alloxan is highly unstable in water, decomposes to give dimethyl urea and meso oxalic acid as shown below.

Since none of the intermediates could be detected, Scheme 1 is only one of the possible mechanisms for the reaction in the absence of free radical. Attempts were made to allow spectrophotometric detection of $[\text{Mn}^{\text{V}}]$ and $[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]$ ion intermediates as the reaction proceeded in the oxidation of caffeine by acidic MnO_4^- ion. Unfortunately, the low concentration of Mn^{3+} and Mn^{5+} intermediates obtained under our experimental conditions made the detection unsuccessful. However there are reports of their existence in the earlier literature³². Scheme 1 leads to the rate law (3), which explains all the observed orders.

$$-\frac{d[\text{MnO}_4^-]}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{H}]_T[\text{MnO}_4^-]_T[\text{Caf.}]}{(1 + K[\text{H}^+]) (1 + K[\text{MnO}_4^-])} \quad (5)$$

$$= \frac{kK[\text{H}^+] [\text{Caf.}] [\text{MnO}_4^-]}{1 + K[\text{H}^+] + K[\text{MnO}_4^-] + K^2[\text{H}^+] [\text{MnO}_4^-]} \quad (6)$$

The terms such as $K[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ and $K^2[\text{H}^+][\text{MnO}_4^-]$ in the denominator of eq. (6) are negligible in view of the low concentration of $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ used in the experiments. Hence eq. (6) becomes (7).

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{MnO}_4^-]} = \frac{kK [\text{H}^+] [\text{Caf.}]}{1 + K[\text{H}^+]} \quad (7)$$

The mechanism of Scheme 1 and rate law (3) may be verified by rearranging in the form

$$\frac{[\text{Caf.}]}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{kK[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (8)$$

where k_{obs} is first order rate constant. According to eq. (8), the plot of $[\text{Caf.}]/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{H}^+]$ ($r > 0.9996$, $s \leq 3.2868$) is expected to be linear, which is verified in Fig. 4. The slope and intercept of such plot lead to the values of K and k at 25 °C as $4.5995 \pm 0.18 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $0.1819 \pm 0.0073 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. Using these values the experimental rate constants can be computed. The negligible effect of ionic strength and relative permittivity on rate is qualitatively consistent with reaction between two neutral molecules as in Scheme 1. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are both consistent with an electron transfer process.

Fig. 4. The plot of $[\text{Caf.}]/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ (verification of rate law (3)) (conditions as in Table 1).

Experimental

Materials and method :

Caffeine was purchased from Sigma and used as received. The solubility of caffeine is appreciable hence the solution of caffeine was always prepared afresh using double distilled water. All other chemicals used were of BDH, AnalaR or imported specifications. Potassium permanganate (BDH) was prepared in doubly distilled water and its strength was ascertained^{20(a)} by titrating against standard $\text{H}_2(\text{CO}_2)_2$ solution in hot acidic medium, hence it was prepared in water. Perchloric acid (Merck) and sodium perchlorate (BDH) were used to provide the required acidity and ionic strength respectively. Mn^{II} was prepared by dissolving manganese(II) sulphate (Riedel). Doubly distilled conductivity water was used to prepare all the solution.

Kinetic studies :

Kinetic measurements were performed on a Systronic spectrophotometer connected to a rapid kinetic accessory (HI-TECH SFA-12). Optical density versus concentration plot for acidified permanganate ion showed that Beer's law under the reaction conditions in $6.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in $0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$ is obeyed at wave length of 526 nm and molar absorptivity of permanganate was found to be $2300 \pm 50 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is in good agreement with previous results²¹.

All kinetic measurements were performed under pseudo-first order conditions where [caffeine] was always ≥ 10 fold in excess over $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ at a constant ionic strength of 2.5 mol dm^{-3} in acidic medium at a constant temperature of $25 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The progress of the reaction was followed by monitoring the decrease in MnO_4^- in a 1 cm quartz cell of a Systronic model spectrophotometer at its absorption maximum, 526 nm as a function of time. Earlier it was verified that there is negligible interference from other reaction species at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constants were obtained from the plots of log absorbance versus time. The plots were linear up to 80% completion of the reaction and k_{obs} values were reproducible within $\pm 5\%$ (Fig. 1). During the progress of the reaction, the color of the solution changed from violet to colorless, which is verified by a spot test for Mn^{II} ^{20(b)}. The formation of Mn^{II} is represented in Fig. 2.

In order to obtain the regression coefficient, r and standard deviation, s of plots from the regression line, a regression analysis of experimental data was performed with an Intel personnel computer.

Conclusion

In acid medium, Mn^{II} as the reduced product of Mn^{VII} in the reaction may suggest that caffeine shows strong reducing character in HClO_4 medium. The overall mechanistic sequences described in the media are consistent with product, mechanistic and kinetic studies, 1,1-dimethyl urea ($\text{H}_2\text{NCON}(\text{CH}_3)_2$) and 1,3-dimethyl urea ($\text{CH}_3\text{HNCONHCH}_3$) have been investigated in the light of NLO applications. N-Methyl urea ($\text{H}_3\text{CNHCONH}_2$) is one of the promising organic non-linear optical materials for ultraviolet conversion.

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Appendix

According to Scheme 1,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= k[\text{HMnO}_4][\text{Caf.}] \\ &= kK[\text{MnO}_4^-]_f [\text{Caf.}]_f [\text{H}^+]_f \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A1})$$

The total concentration of $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ is given by (where

'T' and 'f' stand for total and free)

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{MnO}_4^-]_T &= [\text{MnO}_4^-]_f + [\text{HMnO}_4] \\ &= [\text{MnO}_4^-]_f (1 + K[\text{H}^+]) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$[\text{MnO}_4^-]_f = \frac{[\text{MnO}_4^-]_T}{1 + K[\text{H}^+]} \quad (\text{A1a})$$

Similarly,

$$[\text{H}^+]_f = \frac{[\text{H}^+]_T}{1 + K[\text{MnO}_4^-]} \quad (\text{A1b})$$

Substituting eqs. (A1a) and (A1b) in eq. (A1),

$$\text{Rate} = - \frac{d[\text{MnO}_4^-]}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{H}^+][\text{Caf.}][\text{MnO}_4^-]_T}{(1 + K[\text{H}^+])(1 + K[\text{MnO}_4^-])} \quad (\text{A1c})$$

The term $(1 + K[\text{MnO}_4^-])$ in the denominator of eq. (A1c) approximates to unity in view of low concentration of MnO_4^- used.

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